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BIOLOGY PROJECT

**Behavioral responses of seahorses to conspecific sounds: insights into
biological function of sound production during feeding**

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.ABSTRACT	3
2.INTRODUCTION	4
2.1 Importance of sounds in animal communication.....	4
2.2 Biological and ecological characterization of seahorses.....	5
2.3 Function of sound production in seahorses.....	6
2.4 Objective of the study and future research.....	7
3.MATERIAL AND METHODS	8
3.1 Study setting.....	8
3.2 Aquariums and seahorse maintenance	8
3.3 Experimental setup.....	9
3.4 Experimental procedure.....	10
3.5 Data analysis.....	10
3.6 Statistical analysis.....	11
4.RESULTS	12
4.1 Last choice.....	12
4.2 Time spent in the last choice.....	13
4.3 Total swimming time.....	14
4.4 Total number of choices.....	14
5.DISCUSSION	16
6.CONCLUSION	18
7.BIBLIOGRAPHY	19
8. APPENDIX	21

1. ABSTRACT

Sound communication is crucial for many animals in several social contexts. Different from the land vertebrates that vocalize through vibration of vocal cords, marine animals have developed different mechanisms for acoustic communication due to physical properties of the water. Seahorses are among the animals that employ sounds in various behavioral contexts such as feeding and reproduction. This study aims to examine how seahorse species *Hippocampus hippocampus* and *Hippocampus guttulatus* respond to sounds made by their conspecifics during feeding and whether they exhibit attraction (phonotaxis) towards the sound emission. The experiment was conducted at the Laboratório Marítimo da Guia (Cascais) where seahorses were kept in saltwater tanks. Sound recordings were emitted through underwater speakers, and the seahorses' behaviour was observed and recorded for ten minutes. The results showed that a significant majority of individuals from both species ($91.57\% \pm 11.79\%$ for *H.guttulatus* and $16,67\% \pm 18,26\%$ for *H. hippocampus*) preferred the area of the tank where the active speaker was located, indicating an attraction to conspecific acoustic signals. In particular, individuals of *H. hippocampus* showed significantly more time spent in the final choice area compared to *H. guttulatus*, suggesting possible species-specific differences in phonotaxis. These findings provide a more profound comprehension of the role of sound communication in the seahorses and contribute to the knowledge about biology and ecology of these species. There is a need for further research to identify the function of different sound types among seahorses as well as understand how acoustic communication evolves in various ecological and social contexts.

Key-words: Seahorses, Conspecific sounds, Acoustic signalling, Behavioral responses

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Importance of sound in animal communication

All animals rely heavily on their ability to communicate with other individuals [1] in order to find mates, establish territories, warn of predators, form groups and maintain the cohesion essential for hunting, migration and social bonding, and to perform a variety of other functions [1,2,3]. Since the physical characteristics of the environments in which aquatic animals live differ from those of terrestrial animals, their ability to communicate is different [3].

Terrestrial vertebrates mainly rely on acoustic communication, producing sounds by vibrations of their vocal tract and detecting them through the tympanum membrane and cochlea. On the other hand, marine vertebrates had to adapt to the characteristics of their habitats, the seawater, by developing new and different mechanisms for sound production and detection. For instance, they are able to use the swim bladder or pectoral fins for sound generation, and they use mechanoreceptors (sensory hair cells) located in their inner ear otolithic endorgans to perceive them [4].

In addition to acoustic and visual communication, aquatic animals are able to communicate through chemical signals, such as the release of pheromones, as well as through electrical and vibrational discharges.

Acoustic communication is not a property present in all fish species: many taxa, such as cartilaginous fishes or many bony fish species, are unable to generate acoustic signals [4]. On the other hand, all fish species possess the inner ear for the perception of sounds, and some have also developed accessory structures, such as auditory ossicles, to enhance hearing [5].

Many marine animals use acoustic signals to perform a multiplicity of biological activities, such as communication, protection, locating food, navigating underwater and understanding their environment [6].

Sounds are particularly important in communication because they allow a large amount of information to be transmitted very quickly and over long distances. Aquatic organisms, including marine mammals, fish, and invertebrates, are capable of producing sounds with emission frequencies ranging from infrasound to ultrasound [6].

The difference in sounds produced reveals differences not only between species in the same family, but sometimes also within species (individual differences), and this variability has been shown to play an important role in the social life of fish. The diversity of sounds produced by conspecifics or heterospecifics can be used in contexts of reproductive isolation, partner choice, opponent evaluation, or competitor identification. Many fish, especially males, make sounds to attract partners to the spawning site, demonstrating how sound production plays a crucial role in mate selection and territory defense [6].

2.2 Biological and ecological characterization of seahorses

Seahorses are represented only by the genus *Hippocampus*, included in the family *Syngnathidae*, together with pipefishes, pipehorses and seadragons [7]. This family belongs to the order of *Gasterosteiformes* [8], within the class of *Teleostei* [7]. The classification and taxonomy of seahorses still requires clarification [9].

They all exhibit the same characteristic morphology: they possess a horse-like head, set at right angles to the body, with a long, tube-shaped snout for sucking in food and eyes that rotate independently [9]. There is no distinct stomach in the digestive tract, and the skin is spread over apparent bone plates in the absence of scales. They only have a propulsive dorsal fin, two pectoral fins that resemble ears and serve to stabilize swimming, a reduced anal fin, and no pelvic or caudal fins (instead of which they have a prehensile tail) [9].

Males and females do not significantly differ in size, with total heights ranging from 20 to 300 mm (measured from the crown to the tip of the straightened tail) [9]. Several studies reveal variations in the caudal pouch, which is unique to males, and a sexual dimorphism in body proportions. In order to support the caudal bag or gain an advantage in the coupling competition, the latter have a longer tail.

In addition to having excellent mimetic skills, seahorses are capable of shifting their color to better match with their surroundings. They may additionally exhibit skin filaments to help them better mimic with their habitat and to avoid predators [8,9]. Typically, they are beige, black, or brown, with other possible variations and when they interact with each other, they frequently change color quickly, especially when they are mating or stressed [9].

The main stereotyped behaviors included in previously reported ethograms are: swimming, in which the animal swims actively; the "fast body movement", "head movement," in which

the animal moves its head slowly while its body remains immobile; and finally, stationary, when the animal does not move [10].

The seahorses are carnivores, and their feeding strategy is to wait for the prey to approach their mouth, and then eat it through a water suction mechanism. Their diet consists of small crustaceans, nematodes, polychetes and small fish [9].

They are distributed all over the world, and genetic evidence suggests that they originated at least 20 million years ago, although many other species are thought to have originated much more recently [9]. They are only found in shallow, temperate and tropical waters, where they inhabit typical coastal habitats. Tropical species are primarily found in coral reefs, whereas temperate species are primarily found in the habitats of seagrass meadows and algae [9].

2.3 Function of sound production in seahorses

Sound production in seahorses presumably serves several biological functions, mainly concerning social communication and reproduction.

The production of sounds has been studied in various species of seahorses, including *Hippocampus hippocampus* [11], and the predominant acoustic signals detected have been described as “clicks”, which are emitted mainly during feeding, courtship, stress situations, male-male competition and when animals are introduced into new environments [12].

Oliveira et al. (2009) [12], conducted a study to test and analyze the sound production of *Hippocampus reidi* and *Hippocampus erectus*, during feeding, courtship and manipulation. As for the clicks produced during the feeding, the functional meaning of these sounds is currently unknown. They were also recorded in unsuccessful attempts, which suggested that they were not associated with success in capturing prey, according to the study. The production of these clicks may be utilized to alert a partner to the presence of food, as suggested by Anderson's PhD thesis (2009) [13].

According to Oliveira et al. (2009) [12] both species—*H. reidi* and *H. erectus*—produce sounds during courtship, especially during the last day before coupling. Furthermore, the sounds made during feeding were louder than the sounds made during courtship, which may indicate this types of sound have different functions or different receivers.

A different kind of sound, analogous to a "grumbling" connected to a body vibration, has also been documented when animals are being handled. Although it has been hypothesized that

stressful circumstances, such as holding the animal in the hand or maintaining it out of the water, cause this distinct sound, more investigation is required to fully comprehend this behavior [13].

Other possible functions of the emitted sounds could include the localization and identification of conspecifics, mate selection, to signal social status, and territorial defence. In addition, these sounds could serve as alarms to signal the presence of predators and potential threats. However, there are still many uncertainties about the specific functions of vocalizations of these fish.

2.4 Objective of the study and future research

This study aimed to examine whether the seahorses *Hippocampus hippocampus* and *Hippocampus guttulatus* respond with attraction (phonotaxis) to sounds produced by conspecifics during feeding, in a lab controlled environment using a sound playback experimental setup. In addition, the study intended to identify potential changes in behavioral patterns, such as overall swimming activity.

The results of this study aim to contribute to a better understanding of the function of acoustic communication in seahorses behavior and its relevance for the ecology and reproductive biology of these fish.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 Study setting

The study was conducted in the aquaculture facilities of the Laboratório Marítimo da Guia, MARE, from Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa, located in Cascais, Portugal.

The present research and analysis was reviewed and authorized by the Faculty of Science of the University of Lisbon (ORBEA), in accordance with the requirements imposed by Legislative Decree 113/2013 and EU legislation (Directive 2010/63/EU) on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes.

3.2 Aquariums and seahorse maintenance

Both species *H. hippocampus* and *H. guttulatus* were randomly distributed and maintained within three semi-open aquarium systems, consisted of three 70-liter aquariums and a common water outflow tank.

All aquariums were equipped with artificial plants, chains, and plastic networks, among other environmental enrichment structures. These components have enhanced animal welfare by creating habitats and anchoring points for these animals. To maintain oxygen levels, each sump included an air compressor (Mebo Blower LA-80B, NITTO KOHKI) that was connected to an air diffuser in each aquarium.

The seahorses were maintained under controlled conditions optimal for their well-being, similar to those found in their natural environment. Daily, the tanks were subjected to regular maintenance, which included cleaning the tanks, changing the water, monitoring the physico-chemical parameters of the water, and feeding the seahorses *ad libitum* with frozen mysis and artemia.

Water parameters monitored on a daily basis were temperature, maintained in a range of 16.5°C to 17.5°C, dissolved oxygen content maintained in percentages of ~100%, pH, maintained at 8.0 ± 0.2 , values measured through the Multi3510 SET 4, WTW, and salinity, maintained in a range of 34 ± 1 and measured through the Refractometer, TMC.

Among the parameters monitored periodically, but less frequently than those mentioned above, are ammonium, nitrite, and nitrate concentrations, maintained below values of, respectively, 0.2, 0.1, and 10.0 (mg/L), measured through the Nitrite / Nitrate Combination Test Kit instrument, TMC.

3.3 Experimental setup

The experiments were conducted in an additional tank measuring 115 cm in length, 50 cm in width, 37 cm in height, with a thickness of 1 cm, containing about 160 L of seawater. The seawater was maintained under ideal conditions for seahorse well-being, with parameters such as temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and pH monitored using the same procedures as those adopted in the maintenance tanks.

Two underwater speakers (UW30, Electro-Voice, MN, EUA) were placed at the two opposite sides of the tank. For each session, one speaker emitted playback sounds produced by the species being tested, and the other speaker remained connected to the system, but without sound playback. The sounds were spaced by intervals of 4 to 5 seconds of silence.

A computer running the bioacoustics software Raven Pro, version 1.6.5 (Bioacoustic Research Program, Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology, NY, EUA) was connected to an audio amplifier (XMN1004 4/3/2 Channel 1000-Watt Amplifier, Sony, Portugal), which was connected to a power supply (12VDC 16.5A 200W OR-ZL-1636, Orno, Portugal) and to the underwater speakers.

Previous studies (e.g., Anderson, 2009 [15]) indicated that certain seahorse species produced sounds averaging 130 dB re 1 μ Pa. Hence, a hydrophone (Brüel & Kjaer 8104) connected to a sound level meter (Mediator 2238, Brüel & Kjaer, Denmark) was positioned near the plants. A sound file containing the species sound was played in loop through the computer. The volume was adjusted until the sound pressure reached 130 ± 0.5 dB re μ Pa.

The sounds of each species were previously recorded using a hydrophone (Aquarian Audio H2a-XLR-15, Anacortes, WA; frequency range: 10–100 kHz -4 dB; voltage sensitivity: -180 dB re 1V/ μ Pa) connected to an A/D converter audio interface (Octa-Capture, Roland, Tokyo, Japan), which was then connected to a laptop running the Raven Pro software. Seahorse sounds were recorded for 15 minutes (four times), in different tanks, and they were fed immediately after pressing the record button, to capture feeding clicks.

In order to replicate the conditions of the stock tanks and prevent the stress due to the transfer to a new environment, two artificial plants were positioned 8.5 cm from the speaker on either side of the experimental tank, and sand was distributed throughout the tank's bottom.

3.4 Experimental procedure

The experiments, which involved 30 seahorses- 10 individuals of *Hippocampus guttulatus* and 20 of *Hippocampus hippocampus*—were carried out during 12 days, in the period from March 1 to 25, 2024.

Using a net and a propylene beaker filled with seawater, the seahorses were carefully transferred one at a time from the maintenance tank to the experiment tank. The specimen was identified through the spots on their skin and as either a male or a female through photography before being put in the experimental tank.

After being placed inside the experimental tank, the subject was left for 4 min inside the acclimatization zone, which was defined by two plastic plates placed on either side of this zone, 16 cm from the tank's center, then 32 cm between them. The animal was restricted to the acclimatization zone by these plates, which prevented it from swimming freely throughout the pool and allowed to acclimatize to it. After the acclimatation period, a video recording was made via a mobile device supported by a cabinet positioned above the tank, in a parallel position in order to record the whole tank. Simultaneously, the speaker on the left (or right, depending on the day of the experiments) began playing a recording of the sound of seahorses that belonged to the same species as the seahorses that were being tested. The seahorse was kept in the acclimatization for the sound playback for an additional minute. A minute later, the plastic plates were removed, allowing the individual to swim without restriction in every section of the experimental tank. Animals were recorded during additional 10 min, during which the animal's behavior was observed. Upon the completion of the recording and sound emission, the animal was carefully placed back into the maintenance tank.

After that, the procedure was repeated for all the other seahorses belonging to the same tank.

3.5 Data analysis

The video recordings were examined and analyzed after the experiments were completed, and different parameters were noted in a table created with Microsoft Excel software for Microsoft 365 MSO (Version 2406 Build 16.0.17726.20078).

For each individual tested, the tank from which it was taken, the day, date, and time of the experiment, the speaker that emitted the sound, the total number of choices, the period of time

the animal spent in each choice area, and the total amount of swimming time over the course of the ten minutes, were all noted.

It should be made clear that by "choice," it is meant the seahorse's entry into the area designated as the "choice area", which is the area of the tank near by the speakers and artificial plants

3.6 Statistical analysis

For the statistical analyses, the following variables were considered: species and sex as independent variables; last choice (coded as 1 for the speaker side choice and 0 for the opposite side), time spent in the last choice, total swimming time, and total number of choices as dependent variables.

The analysis of these variables was conducted using RStudio software (Version 1.3.1093 – © 2009-2020 RStudio, PBC) via Generalized Linear Mixed Models. Species and sex were treated as fixed factors, while the last choice, total number of choices, swimming time, and duration of the last choice were treated as numerical variables. For the time variables (swimming time and duration of the choice), the Beta family with a logit link function was used; for the last choice, the Binomial family was employed, while for the total number of choices, the Negative Binomial family was used. All models were tested using the "glmmTMB" function from the "glmmTMB" package and Post-hoc multiple comparisons were performed with the "emmeans" package (Supplementary Table 1-8).

If the p-values are significant, they are grouped based on their values and presented in the tables as follows: * < 0.05, ** < 0.01, and *** < 0.001.

The graphs related to these variables were created using Microsoft Excel software for Microsoft 365 MSO (Version 2406 Build 16.0.17726.20078) based on the calculation of the mean and standard deviation.

4. RESULTS

In this section, the results of the statistical analyses performed on the following variables will be presented: last choice, time spent on the last choice, total swimming time, total number of choices (figure 1-4).

4.1 Last choice

Figure 1 illustrates the number of individuals (in percentage) from the two different species making two distinct choices (choice 1, towards the sound side; choice 0, towards the silent side).

For the species *H. guttulatus*, $91.57\% \pm 11.79\%$ chose the sound side of conspecifics and $8.33\% \pm 11.79\%$ the side without any sound.

Regarding the species *H. hippocampus*, $86,67\% \pm 18,26\%$ chose the side with the noise and the $16,67\% \pm 18,26\%$ the one without.

Overall, 27 individuals chose option 1, while 3 individuals chose option 0. Statistical analyses revealed no significant differences either between the two species or between sexes, as the p-values were > 0.05 (Supplementary Table 1,2).

Figure 1. Final choice of the species *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. The figure shows the % of individuals opting for choice 1 (towards the conspecific sound emission side) or choice 0 (towards the opposite side without any type of sound). Error bars represent the standard deviation.

4.2 Time spent in the last choice

The graph in Figure 2 shows the mean percentage of time spent on the last choice for the species studied, divided by gender (male and female). Error bars represent the standard deviation.

For the species *H. guttulatus*, females show a mean time spent on the last choice of approximately $7\% \pm 6\%$, while males exhibit a mean time of about $13\% \pm 6\%$. Concerning *H. hippocampus*, female individuals have a mean time spent on the last choice of around $74\% \pm 28\%$, whereas males show a mean time of about $67\% \pm 29\%$.

The symbol (***) above the bars indicate a statistically significant difference between the two species, with a p-value of < 0.001 . This suggests that *H. hippocampus* spends significantly more time on the last choice compared to *H. guttulatus*, with a highly significant difference between the species (Supplementary Table 1).

Supplementary Table 2 shows the post-hoc analysis utilized to determine specific differences between species and genders. Females of *H. hippocampus* show significantly higher times compared to females of *H. guttulatus* (p-value < 0.001). Concomitantly, males of *H. hippocampus* exhibit higher times compared to males of *H. guttulatus* (p-value < 0.001). Another significant difference is found between males of *H. hippocampus* and females of *H. guttulatus* (p-value < 0.001). Lastly, a p-value < 0.05 is observed in females of *H. hippocampus* compared to males of *H. guttulatus*.

Figure 2. Mean time spent on the last choice for females (F) and males (M) of *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. Error bars represent the standard deviation. (***) indicates a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$) between species.

4.3 Total swimming time

In Figure 3, the graph shows the mean swimming time in percentage for the two studied species, differentiated by gender, male and female. The error bars are the standard deviation. As for *H. guttulatus*, the swimming time of the female individuals is equal to $24\% \pm 20\%$. Males have a mean swimming time of approximately $22\% \pm 11\%$, while for the species *H. hippocampus*, females have a mean swimming time of around $21\% \pm 12\%$, while males have mean swimming time of $17\% \pm 18\%$. Although swimming time decreased between sex of each species, the statistical results show no significant differences between the sexes and between the species, $p > 0.05$ (Supplementary Table 1,2).

Figure 3. Mean swimming time (in percentage) for females (F) and males (M) of *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

4.4 Total number of choices

In Figure 4, is showed the total number of choices during the experiments made by male and female individuals of the two species under study.

For *H. guttulatus*, the graph shows a mean number of choices of 1.7 ± 1.2 for females and 1.3 ± 0.5 for males. In the species *H. hippocampus*, values of 2.1 ± 2.5 are reported for females and 2.5 ± 2.2 for males.

Statistical analyses report p-values < 0.05 , indicating no significant differences in the number of choices between the species or between males and females within each species (Supplementary Table 1,2).

Figure 4. Mean number of choices made by male (M) and female (F) individuals of *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. Error bars represent the standard deviation.

5. DISCUSSION

The study intended to analyze the behavioural response of two species of seahorses, *Hippocampus hippocampus* and *Hippocampus guttulatus*, when subjected to sounds emitted by conspecific individuals during the feeding context, and to identify potential patterns in responses.

Previous studies [11,12,13] have documented sound production in seahorses as mainly occurring during feeding, courtship or stress conditions.

Analysis of the last choice reported here showed that a significant majority of individuals of both species preferred the side where the speaker was playing conspecific sounds, indicating a preference for the area where sounds were present. $91.57\% \pm 11.79\%$ of individuals of *H. guttulatus* and $86.67\% \pm 18.26\%$ of individuals of *H. hippocampus* preferred the sound side and $8.33\% \pm 11.79\%$ of *H. guttulatus* and $16.67\% \pm 18.26\%$ of *H. hippocampus* chose the opposite side (Fig. 1), with only one seahorse making no choice and remaining stationary in the acclimation area, which was included as not available (NA) in the statistical analyses. This might suggest that seahorses are able to detect sounds produced by individuals of their species, and are presumably attracted to them, supporting the hypothesis that sound signals play an important role in social interactions, such as attraction to food resources.

Interestingly, while no significant differences were found in the number of individuals choosing the sound side, the time spent in the area of last choice was significantly higher in *H. hippocampus* species than in *H. guttulatus*. On average, males of *H. guttulatus* spent a mean time of $13\% \pm 6\%$ in the area of last choice, while females reported values of $7\% \pm 6\%$. Of the species *H. hippocampus*, females show an average time of $74\% \pm 28\%$, while males record values of $67\% \pm 29\%$. This result could indicate greater or more prolonged involvement with acoustic signals in *H. hippocampus*, which may reflect interspecific differences in the perception of sounds, during social interactions. Nevertheless, additional testes need to be conducted to verify this hypothesis.

For the total swimming time, no significant differences were shown between species or between sexes. This lack of variation could indicate a constant overall level of low swimming activity, suggesting that the presence of conspecific sounds does not induce stress or alter the general behaviors of seahorses.

The total number of choices made by individuals showed no significant differences between species or sexes, and mean values ranged from $1,3 \pm 0,5$ (in males of *H. guttulatus*) to $2,5 \pm 2,2$ (in males of *H. hippocampus*). This low number of choices made, could indicate that seahorses focus more on sound localization, rather than exploratory swimming behaviors.

The results of this study provide very interesting and novel insights about the possible role of acoustic communication in seahorse behavior. The preference of both species for the sound side and the prolonged time that *H. hippocampus* spends in that area suggest that acoustic stimuli are probably used by these animals for social purposes and to identify feeding sites.

These findings appear to be consistent with previous studies that have shown sound production in several seahorse species in courtship, feeding and stress contexts [11,12,13]. However, none of these studies have tested seahorse attraction (phonotaxis) experimentally using sound playbacks as conducted in the present work.

Playback experiments from a previous study [15] on *Pomatoschistus pictus*, the painted goby, demonstrated that when sound is combined with visual stimuli (a male confined in a small aquarium placed near each speaker), females spent more time near the male associated with courtship sounds than the control male (associated with white noise or silence). This provides insight into how acoustic signals are used by fish, for social purposes.

Understanding how seahorses use acoustic signals may contribute to better management and conservation of these threatened species, especially in habitats subject to anthropogenic acoustic disturbance, such as most coastlines and estuaries of Portugal [16]. Human activities, such as underwater navigation or construction, may generate noise that interferes with the acoustic communication of these animals, compromising their important behavioral activities.

Acoustic signals might be used as an instrument to locate and monitor seahorse populations, providing data on the presence and density of the populations and allowing them to be monitored more effectively. In this way, it would also be a useful tool that could be used in the designation of marine protected areas, which would provide a safe and noise-free environment that supports the social and reproductive interactions of these animals.

Finally, future research should focus on the study of interspecific differences in acoustic communication, with the purpose of improving knowledge about the role of sound signals in different social and ecological .

There were some limitations in this study, and these may have slightly compromised the results found. These might include the sample size of individuals used: with a larger sample, the behavior found within seahorse populations could have been better represented and emulated. In addition, although the experiments were conducted in a setting as similar as possible to the natural habitat of these species, differences between the experimental and natural habitat may have provided results that do not fully reflect those occurring in the native environment, where social and environmental conditions are more complex and variable. Moreover, as the experiments were carried out on the species *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*, the results might not be extended to the remaining species of the genus *Hippocampus*, but be limited to the two considered in this study. The restricted time of the experiments may also have compromised the results, as it might not have been sufficient to fully report and reflect the behaviors that would instead occur over longer periods of time.

Future research will be critical to clarify the precise role of sound production in the lives of these animals. Comparative studies among species and populations of seahorses could also reveal how acoustic communication evolves in relation to different ecological and social contexts.

6. CONCLUSION

The results of this work provide important insights into the function of acoustic communication in seahorse behavior, suggesting that acoustic stimuli may be used by these animals for social purposes. These findings are in line with previous studies that have documented sound production in different seahorses species during courtship, feeding and stress responses [11,12,13].

Understanding how seahorses utilize acoustic signals can contribute to the improved management and conservation of this species, especially in habitats subjected to anthropogenic sounds. Sounds could be used as a tool to localize seahorse populations, providing data on their presence and density and enabling more effective monitoring.

To better understand the role of sound signals in various social and ecological contexts and to obtain insight into the ecology and reproductive biology of seahorses, future research might focus on examining interspecific differences in acoustic communication.

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8. APPENDIX

Variable		Estimate	Std. error	Z value	Pr (> z)	
Last choice	Intercept	1,9837	1,1204	1,770	0,0766	
	Species Hh	-0,0600	1,3012	-0,046	0,9632	
	Sex M	0,6244	1,2892	0,484	0,6281	
Time last choice	Intercept	-1,5156	0,4025	-3,765	0,000167	***
	Species Hh	2,4850	0,4835	5,139	2,76E-07	***
	Sex M	0,3587	0,3940	0,910	0,362679	
Swimming time	Intercept	-1,1925	0,2662	-4,479	7,49E-06	
	Species Hh	-0,1271	0,3008	-0,422	0,673	
	Sex M	-0,1351	0,2868	-0,471	0,638	
Total choices	Intercept	0,38334	0,31665	1,211	0,226	
	Species Hh	0,42020	0,34461	1,219	0,223	
	Sex M	0,05689	0,30524	0,186	0,852	

Supplemental Table 1. Results of the Binomial model test on the variable "Last choice", Beta model test on the variables "Time spent in the last choice" and "Total swimming time" and Negative Binomial model test on the "Total choices variable", performed on male and female individuals of the species *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. Significant levels (p-value < α , $\alpha = 0.05$) are represented as: * when p-value < 0.05, ** when p-value < 0.01 and *** when p-value < 0.001.

Variable	Contrast	SE	p.value	
Last choice	Hg F / Hh F	1,382	1,0000	
	Hg F / Hg M	0,690	0,9619	
	Hg F / Hh M	0,994	0,9881	
	Hh F / Hg M	0,965	0,9840	
	Hh F / Hh M	0,690	0,9619	
	Hg M / Hh M	1,382	1,0000	
Time last choice	Hg F / Hh F	0,0403	0,0001	***
	Hg F / Hg M	0,2753	0,7995	
	Hg F / Hh M	0,0357	0,0005	***
	Hh F / Hg M	5,3152	0,0123	*
	Hh F / Hh M	0,2753	0,7995	
	Hg M / Hh M	0,0403	0,0001	***
Total swimming time	Hg F / Hh F	0,342	0,9741	
	Hg F / Hg M	0,328	0,9647	
	Hg F / Hh M	0,500	0,9033	
	Hh F / Hg M	0,448	1,0000	
	Hh F / Hh M	0,328	0,9647	
	Hg M / Hh M	0,342	0,9741	
Total choices	Hg F / Hh F	0,226	0,6205	
	Hg F / Hg M	0,288	0,9976	
	Hg F / Hh M	0,269	0,6932	
	Hh F / Hg M	0,698	0,8764	
	Hh F / Hh M	0,288	0,9976	
	Hg M / Hh M	0,226	0,6205	

Supplemental Table 2. Post-hoc comparison results for the variable "Last Choice", "Time last choice", "total swimming time" and "Total choices" analyzing differences between male and female individuals of the species *H. guttulatus* and *H. hippocampus*. Significant levels (p-value < α , $\alpha = 0.05$) are represented as: * when p-value < 0.05, ** when p-value < 0.01 and *** when p-value < 0.001.